

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**COVID-19: PATHOPHYSIOLOGY, TREATMENT AND
PREVENTION****Ahire Pavan V.¹, Erande Kiran B.², Chavan Saurabh B.³**^{1,3}Student, ²Assistant Professor,^{1,3}Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance,^{1,3}M. G. V.'s Pharmacy College,

Panchavati, Nashik-03, Maharashtra, India.

²MGV'S SPH College of Pharmacy, Malegaon, Dist: Nashik**Abstract:**

Recently, an outbreak of novel corona virus (2019 n CoV) changed the global perspective of healthcare since early December 2019. It has been declared the sixth public health emergency of international concern by the World Health Organization (WHO) and named as corona virus disease 2019 (COVID -19). While over a million people worldwide are now confirmed to be infected with COVID -19, we do not yet have empirical cure or vaccine for this potentially fatal disease. This review highlights origin, transmission, current statistics by WHO (till 11th September 2020), pathophysiology, prevention and treatment approaches for the disease. Currently implemented therapeutic strategy and ongoing clinical trials of the vaccines with respect to the disease has also been discussed in the review. Pathophysiological features are discussed with the help of case report study.

Keywords: COVID-19, Pathophysiology, Treatment, Prevention, Corona virus.

Corresponding author:**Ahire Pavan Vinayak,**

Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance,

M.G.V.'s Pharmacy College, Panchavati, Nashik-03

Email address: pavanahire497@gmail.com

Phone number: 8623033026

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ahire Pavan Vinayak et al, *Covid-19: Pathophysiology, Treatment And Prevention.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

In December 2019, respiratory illness showing symptoms like pneumonia was first identified in Wuhan city, south china. India has 4,562,414 total confirmed cases and 76,271 total new cases of COVID-19 till 11th September 2020. Corona is the Latin word, means 'the crown'. As the virus has crown like protein structure on its surface it is named as corona. Corona virus is the zoonotic virus.

Certain drugs are showing good results for treatment of corona disease 2019(COVID 19) infection. Several industries are trying for the development of vaccine but till now, there is no Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved drug for the treatment of COVID 19 infection. As prevention is better than cure, preventive measures should be followed.

Table 1

Biological name	Sarbecovirus coronaviridae
Class	Pisoniviricetes
Order	Nidovirales
Family	Coronaviridae
Sub-family	Orthocoronavirinae

Current statistics globally as per World Health Organization (WHO): (Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) Situation Report Data as received by World Health Organization from national authorities by 10:00 CEST, 11 September 2020) [1]

Table 2 [1]

Total (new cases in last 24 hours)

	Confirmed cases	Deaths
Globally	27,973,127(283,836)	905,426 (6,109)
Africa	1,101,618	23,515
Americas	14,447,680	501,934
Eastern Mediterranean	2,071,058	54,420
Europe	4,645,519	224,145
South-East Asia	5,171,098	89,793
Western Pacific	535,413	11,606

Origin:

Since 12 December 2019, the epidemic of unknown acute respiratory tract infection broke out first in Wuhan, China, which is possibly related to a seafood market. From the several studies it is predicted that bats are possible potential reservoir of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2). The SARS-CoV-2 is a zoonotic virus. α -/ β -/ γ -/ δ -CoV are the four genera of coronavirus. α - and β -CoV can infect mammals, while γ - and δ -CoV able to infect birds. SARS-CoV and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV) are known β -CoVs, which are able to cause severe and potentially fatal respiratory tract infections. From the studies it was found that the genome sequence of a bat CoV RaTG13 has 96.2% similarity to SARS-CoV-2, whereas SARS-CoV is 79.5% identical. On the basis of this evolutionary analysis and genome sequencing results, bat has been suspected as natural host of virus origin. From bats, SARS CoV -2 infects human, via unknown intermediate hosts. SARS-CoV-2 and SARS- CoV could use same receptor i.e. Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), for causing infection to humans. However, human SARS-CoV-2 and bat CoV might share the same ancestor; bats are not

available for sale in this seafood market. So, there is more possibility of alternative of intermediate hosts like snacks, turtles and pangolin.[2]

Transmission:

Huainan seafood market have been tracked for the primary cases of COVID 19, but as secondary cases occurring at hospitals among nurses and physicians who had extensive contact with COVID-19 patients. Through the respiratory droplets from cough and sneeze of COVID 19 infected patient confirmed to be human to human transmission pathway. The incubation period is average 5 – 14 days. During the incubation period patient may be pre symptomatic but contagious. Furthermore, several individuals who did not have direct contact with the Huainan seafood market were diagnosed. The predominant modes of transmission is respiratory droplets or secretions of infected individuals from human to human. The spread of infection is more rapid for the current outbreak than SARS epidemic. Between family members, including relatives and friends who intimately contacted with patients or incubation carriers are mainly showing human to human transmission of SARS-CoV-2.[2,3]

Fig 1: Transmission pathway of COVID-19 [4]

Pathophysiology:

The SARS-CoV-2 shares similarities with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) in genome, sequence, biological behavior, clinical manifestations.

Structure of corona virus:

Fig. 2. Structure of COVID-19 Virus [5]

Four major structural proteins are found in the 2019nCoV,

1. Spike surface glycoprotein (S): It attaches to host receptor Angiotensin Converting Enzyme 2 (ACE2), including two subunit S1 and S2. S1 determines the virus host range and cellular tropism by Receptor Binding Domain (RBD). S2 mediates virus cell membrane fusion by Heptad Repeats 1 (HR1) and Heptad Repeats 2 (HR2).
2. Matrix protein (M): It is responsible for the transmembrane transport of nutrients, the bud release and the formation of envelope.
3. Small envelope protein (E): It is responsible for production and maturation.
4. Nucleocapsidprotein (N): Primarily to bind to the CoV RNA genome, making up the nucleocapsid. [2,6]

TARGET PROTEIN (RECEPTOR) & BINDING:

Fig.3. SARS CoV interaction with receptor-binding domain, specific cell receptors (ACE2), and host cellular transmembrane serine protease (TMPRSS)[7]

About 73% binding affinity of 2019-nCoV in comparison with the SARS-CoV. Transmission and pathogenesis of COVID 19 infection from coronaviruses to humans mainly depend on the interactions, from virus attachment, receptor recognition, protease cleaving and membrane fusion, of its transmembrane spike glycoprotein (S-protein) receptor-binding domain, specific cell receptors (ACE2), and host cellular transmembrane serine protease (TMPRSS). In the same host cell TMPRSS2 are co-localized which latter exerts hydrolytic effects responsible for S-protein priming and viral entry into target cells. ACE2 based strategies against COVID-19 such as ACE2 fusion proteins and TMPRSS2 inhibitors should be accelerated into clinical research and development for diagnosis, prophylaxis, or treatment. [8]

Digestive system might be most vulnerable to COVID 19 infection, as after virus infection sudden increase in gastrointestinal wall permeability to foreign pathogen observed, which results in enteric symptoms like diarrhea due to invaded enterocytes malabsorption.[8]

ACE 2 is the main target receptor for the coronaviruses. ACE 2 is membrane bound aminopeptidase plays vital role in cardiovascular system (CVS) and immune system. Spike protein bind to host receptor via the receptor binding domains of ACE 2. ACE 2 protein found in human organs like Respiratory system, Gastrointestinal tract, Lymph node, Thymus, Bone marrow, Spleen, Liver, Kidney and Brain. SARS CoV -2 on binding with ACE2 receptors binding domains starts to invade alveolar epithelial cells, which results in respiratory disorders. ACE 2 release and blood level increases in patients, who are with renin angiotensin- aldosterone system inhibitors treatment (Hypertensive patients). In hypertensive and diabetes patients, this SARS CoV-2 infection result in worst condition, as it produces increased level of ACE2. Inhibitors of renin angiotensin aldosterone system (RAAS) leads to the risk in hypertension, inflammatory lung diseases, cancer, diabetes treatment, so, alternative antihypertensive treatment should be taken in consideration. [9,10]

Symptoms:

Basically, two type of symptoms are observed in COVID 19 patients, those are as follows:

Table 3

Systemic disorders	Respiratory disorders
Fever	Rhinorrhea
Fatigue	Sneezing
Sputum production	Sore throat
Haemoptysis	Pneumonia
Acute cardiac injury	Ground – glass opacities
Hypoxia	Acute respiratory distress syndrome
Dyspnoea	
Lymphopenia	
Diarrhea	

High risk patients (like diabetes) undergoes severe clinical condition which is expressed in **Fig 5**.

Fig 4: Different organ damage in high risk diabetes patients on SARS Co V -2 infection [11]

Pathological findings as per case report:[12]

According to literature survey, following pathological findings are observed with one of the case report. Biopsy sample of liver, lung, and heart tissue of the patient, who died with COVID-19 shown alter histological examination (Bilateral diffuse alveolar damage with cellular fibromyoxid exudates).

Table 4

Right lung	Left lung
Desquamation of pneumocytes	Pulmonary oedema hyaline membrane formation
Hyaline membrane formation	Early Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome(ARDs)

This finding indicated acute respiratory distress syndrome. Pathological features of covid-19 resemble to SARS and MERS.

Heart: Few intestinal mononuclear inflammatory infiltrates are observed.

Liver: Moderate micro vesicular steatosis and mid lobular portal activity are observed.

Blood:

- Count of peripheral cluster of differentiation 4 (CD4) and cluster of differentiation 8 (CD8) T lymphocyte cells substantially reduced.
- Increased concentration of highly pro inflammatory CCR6+ Th17 in CD4 T cell.
- Over activation of T cells manifested by increased of T helper 17 cells (Th17) and high cytotoxicity of CD8 T cells.
- It causes severe immune injury in this patient (lymphopenia).

Prevention: [13,14]

In COVID-19 like contagious diseases are controlling steps by WHO has stated that education, isolation, prevention, controlling, transmission and treatment of infected persons are major problems to control disease. Therefore, minimize the spread of infection to people and reduce the growth rate making some recommendations. As there is no promising cure is available for the disease, preventive measures should be strictly followed to avoid the disease growth rate. Following preventive recommendations are followed by the public, on government's announcement,

- Staying at home: The people stay isolated in home and avoiding contact with person flu-like symptoms.
- Home quarantine: The person is recommended to stay isolated either in home or in workplace.
- Avoiding unnecessary travelling: Avoid sharing vehicle, avoid crowd or close contact people and also room, in gathering especially picnic place, hill station, visiting hospital, clinic or any other public place.
- Social distancing: Avoiding crowded places like school, college, railway station, bus stop and maintaining minimum two-meter distance between person.

- Washing hands: With the help of soap, water, alcohol (60%) based hand sanitizer cleaning hands for 30 seconds. In coughing and sneezing condition avoid the shaking hands. Do not touch to eyes, nose and mouth.
- Disinfecting surfaces: Surface in home, office and hospitals (door handle, window) should be cleaned up with the wipes and disinfectant.
- Masks: Mask is prevention of the viral infection transmission. Medical mask like N95 and respirator (FFP3) could help to minimize direct exposure to respiratory droplet.
- The person that are COVID19 suspect or shows symptoms call emergency medical services.

Ayurvedic preventive measures:[15]

From ancient times, it is well known that whenever there is outbreak of viral infection or flu like infections, Ayurveda principles and its approaches in India found very effective for prevention and cure. Severe condition of COVID 19 infection can cause acute cardiac injury, acute respiratory syndrome, pneumonia, kidney failure, multiple organ damage. The important characteristics of COVID 19 are elevated level of C –reactive protein (CRP), lymphopenia and impaired immunity. COVID 19 disease severity associated with secondary haemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis, which is characterized by raised levels Interleukin-2 (IL-2), Interleukin-7 (IL-7), granulocyte-colony stimulating factor, interferon- γ , inducible protein 10, monocyte chemo attractant protein 1, macrophage inflammatory protein 1- α and tumour necrosis factor - α (TNF- α).

According to one of the literature surveys, some of the ayurvedic formulations has shown good results in prevention and treatment of COVID-19. As drug repurposing is helping to treat COVID-19, in same way ayurvedic formulations are helping to treat symptoms. From studies of consensus survey, ayurvedic preventive measures and treatment options are helping to cure asymptomatic, mild, moderate and severe clinical conditions identified which are mentioned below in the **Table 5**.

Table 5: Ayurvedic preventive measures [15]

For apparently healthy individual with no symptoms and signs of COVID 19	For high risk/geriatric /presymptomatic phase of COVID19/declared self isolation	For asymptomatic positive cases of COVID 19	For uncomplicated COVID 19 infected patients
Decoction of Sunthi, Lavang, Pippali, Marachi, Cinnamon bark, Tejapatra	Sudarsana Ghana vati 250 mg	Sudarsana Ghana vati	Sudarsana Ghana vati
Haridra milk	Gudduchi tablet/ Samsamanavati 250 mg	Gudduchi Tablet	Amrutadikasayam
Cow milk	Nitya Rasayana Haridra milk or cow ghee	Nitya rasayana	Sanjeevani vati-125 mg
ChyawanprashAvaleha	ChyawanprashAvaleha	Haridra milk or cow ghee	Arogyavardhini Rasa-250 mg
Aswagandha tablet	Sarjja rasa	Vyagriharitaki	Talisadichurna
AmalakiChurna	Pranayama	KusmandaAvaleha	Purna Chandra rasa 125 mg
Neem leaves		Agathiharitaki	SadangaPaneeya
Sarjja rasa		Bilwadigulika -125 mg	Vyagriharitaki
Hingu		Siddha Makardwaja - 125 mg	Suvarnavasantamalati rasa -125 mg

Ayurveda is to maintain equilibrium status of the body tissue. According to Ayurveda, progression of the disease must stopped at early stages. Basically when it is infectious disease, stopping further progression of disease is always ideal, by innate or acquired immunity development. Most of the recommended Ayurveda formulations are advised by the Ministry of Ayush. Decoction of sunthi, Maricha, Lavanga advised to healthy individuals as it improves humoral and cell mediated immunity, as well as reduces airways hyper-responsiveness and nasal congestion. Ghee is known for the upregulation of immune function. Haridra milk blocks cytokine release as it has active constituent of curcumin. Suppression of cytokines has shown clinical improvement in flu and infectious disease. Chyawanprash acts as a immune-boosting agent as it strengthen the respiratory tract as it can treat respiratory problems. Sudarsana Ghana vati has shown good results in allergic rhinitis and malarial fever. Gudduchi tablet in viral infection acts as potent immunomodulator. Tulsi is also one of the good antiviral agent in the disease viral encephalitis.[16]

Treatment: [16,17]

There is no Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved drug available till the date but certain drugs repurposed and has surprisingly shown good therapeutic results in the cure of the COVID-19 disease, so the important and the effective drugs giving good therapeutic results have come to the focus are listed below,

- 1) Hydroxychloroquine: Hydroxychloroquine is used as antimalarial and aminoquinolines, effective result against in COVID 19. Increases pH in endosomes and prevent virus

particles (SARs-CoV and SARs-CoV-2) from use their activity and entry into the cell. It inhibits post translational modification of virus envelope glycoproteins inside the endoplasmic vesicles and trans- Golgi network.

- 2) Remdesivir: Remdesivir is used as antiviral agent. Incorporate into nascent viral RNA chains and result in premature termination.
- 3) Chlorpromazine: It is a antipsychotic agent inhibiting clarithrin mediated endocytosis.
- 4) Dexamethasone: Dexamethasone used as anti-inflammatory drug. It is used for to treat condition such as arthritis and asthma. In COVID-19 disease can have severe lung inflammation scientists wanted to see if dexamethasone can be used to treat that condition.
- 5) Teicoplanin: It is antibacterial agent. Teicoplanin mainly inhibit low pH cleavage of spike protein by cathepsin L in the late endosomes. It stops the genomic viral RNA release and persistence of replication of virus.
- 6) Oritavancin, Dalbavancin and Telvavancin: These drug are glycoprotein antibiotic. It inhibits the entry of SARs-CoV, Ebola virus, MERs-CoV transcription and replication competent virus like particles.
- 7) Chlorpromazine: Antipsychotic agent inhibiting clarithrin mediated endocytosis.
- 8) Nitazoxanide: It treat the parasitic infection, selectively blocks the viral hemagglutinin intracellular trafficking and insertion of this protein in into host plasma membrane.
- 9) Combinatorial therapy approach using hydroxychloroquine (antimalarial) and

- nitazoxanide (treat the parasitic infection): Hydroxychloroquine inhibits viral entry and fusion while nitazoxanide up regulate innate immune response to prevent ongoing viral replication.
- 10) Tocilizumab: Immunosuppressive and antirheumatoid agent. It reduces clinical symptoms of viral infection.
 - 11) Baricitinib: Baricitinib is antirheumatoid agent. It targets endocytosis process and by Adapter-Associated Protein Kinase 1 (AAK1) disruption interrupts passage and assembly of the virus particles.
 - 12) Azithromycin: Macrolide antibiotic, immunomodulatory properties are beneficial to treat pulmonary infection.
 - 13) Hydroxychloroquin (antimalarial) along with liponavir and ritonavir (antiviral): It affects proteolysis in coronavirus replication cycle.
 - 14) Favipiravir: It is used as anti-flu agent. Safe and effective in treatment of COVID 19 patients.
 - 15) Ascorbic acid (vitamin C): It is used as antioxidant. Inhibition of cytokine surge activation and neutrophils get accumulated in lungs, destroy alveolar capillaries.

Table 6: New drugs and treatment approval in India

Drugs	Category	Status	What it does	Uses	Mode of delivery
Remdesivir	Antiviral	Approved	Stop the viral replication in the body.	Given to hospitalized patients on oxygen with moderate COVID 19	Intravenously in ICU.
Glucocorticoids	corticosteroid	Approved	Pumping out inflammatory chemicals	For severely ill patients with progressive deterioration of oxygenation indicators, rapid worsening of imaging and cytokine storm.	Intravenous
Favipiravir	Antiviral	Approved	Inhibiting RNA polymerase and stop replication	For mild to moderate disease	Oral tablet
Dexamethasone	corticosteroid	Approved	Modulates immune mediated lung injury and slows progression to respiratorfailure and death.	Give to severely ill patients on invasive ventilation or oxygenation.it does not use for mild andmoderate disease	Intravenous in ICU and tablet for less seriously ill patients.
Tovilizumab	Monoclonal antibody	Approved	Cytokine storm by acting against inflammatory chemicals to fight infection.	Moderateto severe disease	Intravenous drip
Hydroxycloquine	Antimalarial	Approved	Inhibit the activity of SAR-CoV 2	Prophylaxis for high risk close contact,healthworkers and frontline workers .mild disease at startof infection.	Oral tablet
Convalescent plasma	Plasma therapy	Approved for restricted use.	Infection fighting antibodies from the blood of recovered people given to ill patients to boost their immunity	For patient with moderate disease.	Transfusion

Current Vaccine Status:

There are over 110 perspective projects in works to find a workable cure for SARS-CoV 19. Some have reached to clinical trial stage, others have shown a little less than favorable results. Vaccines requires lot of crucial studies, phases of trials to test out potential side effects to test safety, feasibility and cost. Current status of all the vaccines, which are leading frontrunners right now are listed below,

Table 7: Certain vaccines in preclinical /clinical trials (which are leading front runners right now)

Company	Vaccine	Phase
Pfizer & BioNTech	BNT 162a1 BNT 162b1	Phase 1 Phase 2
Moderna	mRNA1273	Phase 3
Inovio	INO-4800	Phase 1
J&J	Ad26COV2-S	Phase 1
Novavax Inc.	NVX-CoV2373	Phase 1/2
Bharat Biotech	COVAXIN	Phase 2 /3
Cansino Biologics Inc.	Ad5	Phase ssss2

CONCLUSION:

Outbreak of 2019-nCoV has changed the global perspective of healthcare. As till the date there is no working cure is available for the disease, potential therapy is still symptomatic. Based only on hope and optimism, vaccine development may be available till the end of year or more. On the basis of this predictions, at this early time when we don't know about protection against COVID-19, the world needs to learn to manage with this pandemic by strictly following preventive guidelines, this strategy can work if we choose to implement it diligently. High risk patients including hypertensive, Diabetes, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), Cardiovascular patients should be monitored regularly. COVID-19 pandemic has great uncertainty existing. This current pandemic highlighted the importance of Artificial Intelligence enabled drug development. It also made us hyperaware about hygiene, contactless interactions. It strengthened the digital infrastructure. As such cure is not available, prevention must be focused. Social distancing and sanitization showing good results in prevention of COVID-19, but Ayurveda formulations found effective in immunity boosting also requires further research. World is in urgent need of drug and vaccine development against COVID-19 pandemic.

REFERENCES:

- <https://covid19.who.int/>
- Guo, Y.-R., Cao, Q.-D., Hong, Z.-S., Tan, Y.-Y., Chen, S.-D., Jin, H.-J., Tan, K.-S., Wang, D.-Y. and Yan, Y. (2020). The origin, transmission and clinical therapies on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak – an update on the status. *Military Medical Research*, 7(1).
- Peeri, N.C., Shrestha, N., Rahman, M.S., Zaki, R., Tan, Z., Bibi, S., Baghbanzadeh, M., Aghamohammadi, N., Zhang, W. and Haque, U. (2020). The SARS, MERS and novel coronavirus (COVID-19) epidemics, the newest and biggest global health threats: what lessons have we learned? *International Journal of Epidemiology*.
- El Zowalaty, M.E. and Järhult, J.D. (2020). From SARS to COVID-19: A previously unknown SARS- related coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) of pandemic potential infecting humans – Call for a One Health approach. *One Health*, 9, p.100124.
- Parks, J.M. and Smith, J.C. (2020). How to Discover Antiviral Drugs Quickly. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 382(23), pp.2261–2264.
- Tian, S., Xiong, Y., Liu, H., Niu, L., Guo, J., Liao, M. and Xiao, S.-Y. (2020). Pathological study of the 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) through postmortem core biopsies. *Modern Pathology*. [online] Available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41379-020-0536-x.pdf> [Accessed 21 Apr. 2020].
- FPM. (2020). *COVID-19/SARS-CoV-2 Pandemic*. [online] Available at: <https://www.fpm.org.uk/blog/covid-19-sars-cov-2-pandemic/>.
- Gu, J., Han, B. and Wang, J. (2020). COVID-19: Gastrointestinal manifestations and potential fecal-oral transmission. *Gastroenterology*.
- Zheng, Y.-Y., Ma, Y.-T., Zhang, J.-Y. and Xie, X. (2020). COVID-19 and the cardiovascular system. *Nature Reviews Cardiology*, [online] 17, pp.1–2. Available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41569-020-0360-5?fbclid=IwAR3HoFrfs6ePbGvNFTex6jz3dc0yA7Xfw3uwzwKcCLDmZn9nIYejjAuCM88#citeas>.
- Fang, L., Karakiulakis, G. and Roth, M. (2020). Are patients with hypertension and diabetes mellitus at increased risk for COVID-19 infection? *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*.
- Gheblawi, M., Wang, K., Viveiros, A., Nguyen, Q., Zhong, J.-C., Turner, A.J., Raizada, M.K., Grant, M.B. and Oudit, G.Y. (2020). Angiotensin Converting Enzyme 2: SARS-CoV-2 Receptor and Regulator of the Renin-Angiotensin System. *Circulation Research*.
- Xu, Z., Shi, L., Wang, Y., Zhang, J., Huang, L., Zhang, C., Liu, S., Zhao, P., Liu, H., Zhu, L., Tai, Y., Bai, C., Gao, T., Song, J., Xia, P.,

- Dong, J., Zhao, J. and Wang, F.-S. (2020). Pathological findings of COVID-19 associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, [online] 0(0). Available at: [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanres/article/PIIS2213-2600\(20\)30076-X/fulltext?rss=yes&utm_campaign=update-lanres&utm_source=hs_email&utm_medium=email&utm_content=83570178&hsenc=p2ANqtz-9uESUXj_Lm4iXDmvI7dkxjM6zR338P5y63h6v-10exFeWJ3NmnEemsd0SL_ftH9EkPEZ3SiWrzL7vAIGVMdFVtzj32qQ&hsmi=83570178](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanres/article/PIIS2213-2600(20)30076-X/fulltext?rss=yes&utm_campaign=update-lanres&utm_source=hs_email&utm_medium=email&utm_content=83570178&hsenc=p2ANqtz-9uESUXj_Lm4iXDmvI7dkxjM6zR338P5y63h6v-10exFeWJ3NmnEemsd0SL_ftH9EkPEZ3SiWrzL7vAIGVMdFVtzj32qQ&hsmi=83570178).
13. Lotfi, M., Hamblin, M.R. and Rezaei, N. (2020). COVID-19: Transmission, prevention, and potential therapeutic opportunities. *Clinica Chimica Acta; International Journal of Clinical Chemistry*, [online] 508, pp.254–266. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7256510/> [Accessed 20 Jun. 2020].
14. Sajed, A.N. and Amgain, K. (2020). Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) Outbreak and the Strategy for Prevention. *Europasian Journal of Medical Sciences*, 2(1), pp.1–4.
15. Panda, A.K., Dixit, A.K., Rout, S., Mishra, B., Purad, U.V. and Kar, S. (2020). AYURVEDA PRACTITIONERS CONSENSUS TO DEVELOP STRATEGIES FOR PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF CORONA VIRUS DISEASE (COVID-19). *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Sciences (ISSN 2456-3110)*, [online] 5(1), pp.98–106. Available at: <https://www.jaims.in/index.php/jaims/article/view/1102> [Accessed 13 Jul. 2020].
16. Pawar, A.Y. (2020). Combating Devastating COVID -19 by Drug Repurposing. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, p.105984.
17. Comment. (n.d.). [online] Available at: [https://www.thelancet.com/pdfs/journals/laninf/PIIS1473-3099\(20\)30141-9.pdf](https://www.thelancet.com/pdfs/journals/laninf/PIIS1473-3099(20)30141-9.pdf).